

Erythemato Squamous Disease Prediction using Ensemble Multi-Feature Selection Approach

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Abstract— Skin disease dataset has six classes characterized with redundant and noisy features making classification very difficult due to similarities among the classes. To obtain relevant features to the target concept has being a major component in data mining processes. Although, there is no “one-fit-all” model that outperform all others, in this paper, we described a new methodology that combines four different filtering and three embedded feature selection methods to obtain optimal features for individual models and their ensemble for skin disease. On Dermatology datasets, the proposed ensemble method, which is based on machine learning, was able to classify skin disease types into six categories using the one vs many classification approach. The results show that the stacked ensemble obtained 92.9% accuracy, 85.8% sensitivity and 97.4% specificity compared to both single and ensemble classifiers. This paper proves that ensemble learning methods predict skin disease more accurately and effectively.

Keywords: Filtering Method; Embedded Method; Ensemble Learning; SVMs and Erythemato Squamous Disease

I. INTRODUCTION

The human body is covered with the skin totaling 20 square feet area. The skin protects the body from cold, heat, diseases and regulates the body temperature when and where necessary. The skin can be affected by a disease known as erythemato-squamous either through external and genetic factors. Erythemato-squamous disease can be classified into six classes C1: psoriasis, C2: Soborrhic dermatitis, C3: lichen plarus, C4: pityriasis, C5: chronic dermatitis and C6: pityriasis rubra. It is a difficult task identifying and diagnosing skin disease due to the fact that all classes have similar clinical properties with small changes [17, 43 and 42]. Whether it is fungal, allergic-type disease or the viral type, it's critical to identify a skin disease in its early stages. [5] so as to prevent and stop further spread to other parts of the skin. To obtain skin disease parameters for examination by dermatologists, 12 clinical attributes are first examined, if symptom of the disease is found then 22 histopathological attributes are also examined by microscopic analysis. The basic treatment and diagnosis of the skin disease is biopsy. The main challenge dermatologists face when diagnosing skin diseases is that the symptoms of one class of disease can overlap with those of other classes, making treatment and diagnosis extremely difficult [43]. With the advent of artificial intelligence, data mining, machine learning algorithms and ensemble learning techniques being introduced into the field

of medicine, researchers have used different combinations of these methods for the diagnosis, prediction and classification of various medical diseases thereby improving classification performances [39]. These machine learning algorithms have been applied in breast cancer, lung cancer, liver cancer, kidney disease, Erythemato-squamous disease and many more. Machine learning algorithms help to assist the medical professionals in complex diagnosis, prognosis and patient medical monitoring and planning schemes. However, these algorithms do not perform well if the feature set's size is greater than the instances' size. One of the challenges in data quality is high latitude data containing unimportant features which include redundant, irrelevant and noisy features. These unimportant features negatively can affect the performance of the prediction model and processing time complexity [15] because instances with many irrelevant but noisy features provide very little information [35]. Motivated by these limitations, there is the need therefore to obtain optimal performance by applying feature selection method on the medical dataset before classification algorithms are performed.

Ensemble method and feature selection are two current hot topics in machine learning that are widely used to improve single learning machine generalization performance [22]. The concept is based on the idea that combining the output of multiple experts is better than a single expert's output [7], resulting in increased diversity and accuracy of the individual base model. Feature selection was used in [6, 7] as a method for generating diversity in classification ensembles. In this case, diversity was incorporated as a goal in the quest for the best collection of feature subsets. Two different criteria are used to classify feature selection techniques. To begin, it is classified as supervised, unsupervised, or semi-supervised based on the prior knowledge available. Second, it can be divided into filter, wrapper, embedded method (54, 51, 14), hybrid, and ensemble methods [17] depending on how they combine the selection algorithm with model building. Therefore, in this work, we present an ensemble-based multi-filter-multi-embedded feature selection (EMFMEFS) method that combines the output of multi-filter methods: Information gain (IG), Gain ratio (GR), Chi-Squared and ReliefF and multi-embedded methods: Recursive Feature Elimination for Support Vector Machine (RFE-SVM) [11], Prediction Risk-based Feature sElection for Bagging (PRIFEB) of SVMs and Mutual Information based Feature sElection for Bagging (MIFEB) to select only descriptive and informative

features for prediction [23]. The filter technique leverages the descriptive information of the features and is autonomous of the classifier whereas the wrapper and embedding approaches have need of specific learning algorithms to evaluate the feature subset importance. The intrinsic attributes of features are then examined and graded based on distance, dependency, and information measurements [18, 13, and 30]. Hybrid models, on the other hand, combines the benefits of both wrapper and filter techniques [10]. The goals of feature selection are to: reduce time consumption during analysis, remove redundant features, reduces dimensionality, increases interpretability of the models and improve predictive accuracy [46, 29, 25, 13, and 36]. The combination of multiple methods is referred to as ensemble. The ensemble feature selection method uses five machine learning algorithms: support vector machines (SVMs), Decision trees (DT), Nave Bayes (NB), K-nearest neighbour (KNN), and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) and a meta-classifier (logistic regression) on cross-validation to find the set of feature subsets that promote disagreement among the base classifiers while maintaining and improving model accuracy. The erythematosquamous benchmark dataset consisting of 34 features is used to evaluate the efficiency of our proposed method. The rest of the work is organized as follow: related work is presented in section 2. The proposed EMFMEFS method is described in section 3 while section 4 presents the classification algorithms and benchmark dataset. In section 5, our experimental findings are discussed. Section 6 concludes the work.

II. RELATED WORK

Computer-aided diagnostic methods based on data mining and machine learning predictive models can be noninvasive and assist medical experts in making informed diagnosis decisions if based on data gathered using noninvasive techniques. As a result, the patient's suffering is reduced. The performance of a computer-aided diagnostic method depends on the relevance of the selected features with regard to its class. In recent years, features selection methods are applied in the selection of optimal feature subsets for classification in achieving faster and accurate classification models. Two major factors used in the development of a well performing classifier in the field of data mining and machine learning are ensemble feature and model selection [30 and 33]. In the literature, ensemble feature selection helps in the identification of a stable feature subsets that improves prediction performance of any classification models, thereby simplifying their interpretability [19]. Most authors advocate for an ensemble method that shows better performance compared to a single classifier, however, only a few ensemble feature selection methods in their work. This study therefore intends contributing to knowledge by developing an ensemble multi-filter-multi-embedded feature selection (EMFME-FS) method to further reduce the size of the features in the skin disease dataset gathered from UCI repository. Table 1 summarized some of the recent studies reviewed.

II. RELATED WORK

TABLE I
Previous literature review

Author(s)	Classifiers	Feature selection methods	Model accuracy achieved (%) / Metrics	Limitation
[53]	Optimal path forest classifiers.	Pearson correlation coefficient, gain ratio, information gain, reliefF, principal component analysis using greedy-stepwise, best first search.	94.3-96.7	High computational complexity, difficult in analyzing, focus only on homogeneous ensemble methods using optimal path forest classifier. The lack of a lesion segmentation process.
[3]	Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) Fuzzy Extreme Learning Machine (FELM)	-	99.57	Time complexity
[4]	Association rule based a priori algorithm, Fuzzy logic, SVM, AdaBoost, Real, Gentle and Modest Boosting variants	-	99.3 Uses 21 features Reduced dimensionality, Improved complexity, and classification	Data overfitting problem
[40]	SVM, Elephant herding optimization algorithm	-	98.61-99.07	No feature selection
[15]	Random Forest	Chi-Squared, Information gain and Pearson Correlation Coefficient	90.7	Only considered Filter feature selection methods
[55]	SVM-Recursive Feature Elimination, Decision tree, KNN, Naïve Bayes and Neural Networks	Chi-Squared	96.67-100	Limited to one filter based feature selection technique Evolutionary algorithm not considered.
[42]	CART, SVMs, Decision tree, Random forest and Gradient	-	98.64	No Feature Selection

	Boosting Decision tree (GBDT) and Ensemble Method			
[44]	Heat map, SVM, GNB, Decision tree, Logistic regression and Stacking ensemble	Chi-squared, decision importance	97.29% for SVM 99.8% for stacking ensemble	Increased time complexity using different FS instead of combining Feature subsets voting to select same occurring features
[45]	Passive aggressive classifier (PAC), Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Radius Neighbour Classifier (RNC), Bernoulli Naïve Bayes (BNB), Gaussian Naïve Bayesian (NB) and Extra Tree Classifier (ETC) and Bagging, AdaBoost and Gradient Boosting Classifier	Feature importance method (Decision tree)	99.68	Increased time complexity due to the number of features used and the feature selection method.
[39]	Tree based algorithm: C5.0, Credal decision tree, CART, Random Forest (RF), Forest-PA Ensemble methods: RF, Rotation forest, Gradient boosting machine (GBM), Extreme gradient boosting machine (XGB), C- Forest, AdaBoost (AB) Neural based algorithms: DL, MLP, DNN with a stacked auto-encoder (SAEDNN), Linear SVM. Rule based algorithms: Requested incremental	Resampling methods: subsampling, cross validation and multi-round cross validation.	Informed option about the best classifier for disease prediction is provided	No feature selection

	pruning (RIP), Partial decision tree (PART) & OneR.			
[43]	Gaussian Naïve Bayes (GNB), KNN, Decision tree, SVM, Random Forest and MLP	Chi-squared, information gain and principal component.	97.29- 95.94 (Single classifier) 95.94, 97.70 and 99.67 (Ensembl e classifiers)	Limited by filter based feature selection methods.
[32]	SVM, Random forest, Stacking Ensemble, KNN and Naïve Bayes	Information gain and Naïve Bayes as wrapper approach (with Best first, Greedy stepwise and Rank search)	93.8-100	Limited to one filter feature selection method.
[5]	Bagged tree ensemble, k- nearest neighbour (KNN), SVM, ResNet50, VGG16 and GoogleNet.	Grey level co- occurrence matrix (GLCM) and it statistical information. Uses 12 classes	83.33- 92.99 ML classifier, 58.21- 69.23 DL classifier	No feature selection
[16]	ResNet50, ResNeXt50, ResNeXt101, EfficientNet- B4, MobileNetV2, MobileNetV3- Large and MinasNet.	Image balancing, augmentation and Normalization	Applicatio n that allows communic ation in text & upload skin images to have a skin lesion diagnosis	Increased time complexity
[52]	ResNet, InceptionV3, DenseNet, InceptionResNe tV2 and VGG- 19 using transfer learning	-	98 using majority vote and 98.6 using weighted voting	No feature selection

According to a review of the literature, irrespective of the method used, there are three general trends in feature selection: (a) searching and identifying correlated features in the dataset in order to delete redundant features, (b) identifying unique features that contain important information about different output classes in the data and removing features with little or no information, and (c) some features identified are strong as a group but weak individually. The filter feature selection method ranks feature independently based on their ability to predict the output class, whereas the embedded feature selection method selects optimal feature sets based on the algorithm's accuracy. Unlike previous studies, this work presents a novel approach in combining the strengths of both the filter and embedded feature selection method to find the best feature subset using IG, GR, Chi-squared, RFE-SVM, PRIFEB and MIFEB using the skin disease dataset. We therefore reduced the features from 34 to

12 features and used SVMs, DT, NB, K-NN and MLP to evaluate the models.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

This section contains a description of the methods employed in this research. The methodology is divided into four steps. The proposed methodology is illustrated in Fig. 1 in block diagram. The first step is data collection. Then the second step details the feature selection method. The feature selection method is further divided into two steps: multi-filter based feature selection and multi-embedded based feature selection methods. After that, classification models are created using SVM, KNN, DT, NB and MLP and ensemble classifiers by bagging, boosting and stacking. No single model or algorithm can solve all classification problems, according to the "No Free Lunch Theorem" [33]. Using an ensemble model to overcome the drawbacks of a single classifier is one way to do so. Depending on the level of integration, ensemble learning can be divided into feature ensemble and classifier ensemble. Feature ensemble entails combining feature sets that are then fed to a classifier for final output, whereas classifier ensemble entails combining classifier output sets where voting methods are used to determine the final output [17]. By combining multiple sets of classifiers, an ensemble model reduces the variance of error estimation, outperforming individual base classifiers. The final step evaluates the created models using a skin disease dataset, and then compares bagging, boosting, and stacking ensemble to find the best. The results of the ensemble methods are compared to one another, with the best ensemble chosen based on prediction accuracy. As a result, we used feature ensemble and classifier ensemble as ensemble learning methods in this study.

A. Data Sources

The data set used in our study was obtained from UCI machine learning repository (<http://archive.ics.edu/ml>) and the description of the dataset was well explained by [42, 43, 44]. Python 3.7 notebook was used for all the implementations on 64-bit windows 10 pro, core i5, 1.9 GHz processor computer.

B. Dataset Analysis

The skin disease dataset has twelve (12) clinical features and twenty-two (22) histopathological features and six classes as shown in Table 2. The clinical attribute age is nominal attribute. The range of features are defined as:

$$Family\ history\ (f_{11}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{If disease if in the family} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$Other\ attributes = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{no disease found} \\ 1,2 & \text{disease within limit} \\ 3 & \text{high value} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Table II
Skin disease dataset

Classes (no. of instances)	Clinical	Histopathological attributes
C1: Psoriasis (112)	F1: Erythema	F12: Melanin incontinence
C2: Seborrheic dermatitis (61)	F2: Scaling	F13: Eosinophils in the infiltrate

C3: Pityriasis rosea (49)	F3: Definite borders	F14: PNL infiltrate
C4: Chronoc dermatitis (52)	F4: Itching	F15: Fibrosis of the papillary dermis
C5: Lichen planus (72)	F5: Koebner phenomenon	F16: Exocytosis
C6: Pityriasis rubra (20)	F6: Polygonal papules	F17: Acanthosis
	F7: Follicular papules	F18: Hyperkeratosis
	F8: Oral mucosal	F19: Parakeratosis
	F9: Knee and elbow	F20: Clubbing of the rete ridges involvement
	F10: scalp involvement	F21: Elongation of the rete ridge
	F11: Family history	F22: Thinning of the suprapapillary epidermis
	F34: Age	F23: Spongiform pustule
		F24: Munro microabscess
		F25: Focal hypergranulosis
		F26: Disappearance of the granular layer
		F27: Vacuolization and damage of basal layer
		F28: Spongiosis
		F29: Saw-tooth appearance of rete ridges
		F30: Follicular horn plug
		F31: Perifollicular parakeratosis
		F32: Inflammatory mononuclear infiltrate
		F33: Band-like infiltrate

Figure 1: Proposed methodology for Ensemble Multi-Filter-Multi-Embedded Feature Selection (EMFME-FS) Method

C. Feature Selection

Typically, feature selection process as an indispensable component of machine learning is an important preprocessing activity mostly carried out by researchers modeling. Because, a correct selection of the features can lead to an improvement of the inductive learner, either in terms of learning speed, generalization capacity or simplicity of the induced model. The two major approaches in feature selection are individual feature evaluation and feature subset evaluation. The former is also

called the feature ranker, i.e., it assesses individual features by assigning weights according to their degrees of relevance while the latter produces candidate feature subsets based on certain search strategy. In spite of the widely adoption, application and benefits of feature selection techniques in sundry areas, most researchers agree that there is not a so-called “best method” and their efforts are focused on constantly finding a new feature selection method for a specific problem using different strategies: a) combining several feature selection methods, b) combining feature selection approaches with other techniques, c) reinterpreting existing algorithms, d) creating new methods and d) using an ensemble of feature selection methods to ensure better behaviour [8]. Latest development in feature selection methods is hybrid and ensemble methods. While former is less prone to overfitting, the latter is more flexible and robust and both show accurate results with smaller feature subset. However, many researchers put huge and productive efforts in the filter, wrapper, and embedded methods but very few researchers worked on ensemble and hybrid methods. Justification for the use of the proposed feature selection methods- hybrid and ensemble is described in [8, 25]. In this study, the feature selection processes are in two parts: hybrid or multi-filter and embedded-based feature selection methods.

D. Multi-filter based Feature Selection Approach

In this section, we described our proposed ensemble-based multi-filter feature selection methods that combines the output of four filter selection methods: information gain, gain ratio, chi-squared and ReliefF – to harness their combined strength in selecting common features among them using algorithm 1. The justification for choosing these four filter algorithms can be referred in [35, 8, 9, 30, 24].

- Information Gain: information gain is based on the information theory used in selecting the top features by ranking to reduce the feature seize before the state of the learning process. The determination of the uncertainty of each feature prior to ranking is measured using the entropy value of the distribution according to their relevance in determining different classes. The entropy of the distribution, sample entropy or estimated model entropy of the dataset used to determine the uncertainty of the feature. The information gain can be calculated as follow:

$$IG(X|Y) = H(X) - H(X|Y) \quad (3)$$

$$H(X|Y) = \sum_j P(y_j) \sum_i P(x_i|y_i) \log_2 P(x_i|y_i) \quad (4)$$

$$H(X) = - \sum_i P(x_i) \log_2 (P(x_i)) \quad (5)$$

Note $P(x_i)$ denotes the value of prior probabilities of X , $P(x_i|y_i)$ is the posterior probability of X given Y .

- Gain Ratio: The gain ratio improves on the bias of information gain towards features with larger diversity value. When data are evenly spread, gain ratio exhibits a high value while it gives a small value when all data belongs to only one branch of the attributes. It uses both the number and size of branches to determine an attribute and corrects information gain by considering intrinsic information. The intrinsic information of a

given feature can be determined by the entropy distribution of the instance value. The gain ratio of a given feature x and a feature value y can be calculated as follows:

$$Gain\ Ratio(y, x) = \frac{information\ gain(y, x)}{intrinsic\ value(x)} \quad (6)$$

$$intrinsic\ value(x) = - \sum \frac{|S_i|}{|S|} * \log_2 \frac{|S_i|}{S} \quad (7)$$

Note $|S|$ is the number of possible values feature x can take, while $|S_i|$ is the number of actual values of feature x .

- ReliefF: The ReliefF feature selection method evaluates the worth of a feature to distinguish between the nearest but and nearest miss (by using continuous sampling) (nearest neighbour from the same class and from a different class). The attribute evaluate is used to give each feature a weight based on how well it can distinguish between different classes. Important features are chosen based on a user-defined threshold. ReliefF is a fork of the original relief algorithm that was created to address its flaws. ReliefF's ability to deal with the multi-class problem, as well as its robustness and ability to deal with noisy and incomplete data, are among its key features. ReliefF has a low bias and can be used in any situation, which makes it superior to other filter methods. The weight is updated using Equation 8.

$$W[A] = W[A_0] - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^k diff(A, x_i, H)}{(m, k)} + \sum_{C \neq class(x_i)} \frac{p(C)}{1-p(class(x_i))} \cdot \frac{\sum_{j=1}^k diff(A, x_i, M_j(C))}{(m, k)} \quad (8)$$

where attribute weight is W_x , randomly sampled instances are X, R , the nearest hit H , the nearest miss M , m is the number of randomly sampled instances and $diff(A, X_i, H)$ calculates the gap between the values of R for two instances.

- Chi-Square (χ^2): The Chi-Square, based on the χ^2 statistic, measures the feature's independence from the class label. Chi-square score for a feature with x different values and y classes is defined as shown in Equation 9 [20, 48, 2].

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^x \sum_{j=1}^y \frac{(A_{ij} - E_{ij})^2}{E_{ij}} \quad (9)$$

Note that A_{ij} is the number of actual observation (pattern) in the i th attribute (interval), j th class, E_{ij} is the number of expected observation of $A_{ij} = R_i * C_j / N$, R_i is the number of patterns in the i th interval = $\sum_{j=1}^y A_{ij}$ N is the total number of observation = $\sum_{i=1}^x R_i$, C_j is the number of observation in the j th class = $\sum_{i=1}^x A_{ij}$ i, x is the attribute value and y is the number of class label.

The main disadvantages of filter methods are that they avoid interactions with the classifier and that, because most of them are univariate, they consider each feature separately, ignoring feature dependencies. Multivariate filters, on the other hand, model feature dependencies, but at the cost of being less scalable than univariate techniques. However, methods in this

framework are prone to a problem caused by the need to search through feature subsets in the subset generation step, necessitating the use of a combination of filter and embedded methods to maximize their ability to achieve higher classification performance. The combination of the filter-embedded methods improves diversity of individuals and creates an ensemble method which builds a more flexible and robust method that shows more accurate results with smaller feature subset by aggregation of individual results of the classifiers thereby overcoming the instability problem of individual feature selection methods [23, 8, 25, 9]. Table 3 shows some of the advantages and disadvantages of feature selection methods.

Table III
Feature selection techniques

Methods	Advantages	Disadvantages
Filter	Independent of the classifier Lower computational cost than wrapper Fast Good generalization ability	No interaction with the classifier
Wrapper	Interaction with the classifier Captures features dependencies	Computationally expensive Risk of overfitting Classifier-dependent selection
Embedded	Interaction with the classifier Lower computational cost than wrappers Captures features dependencies	Classifier-dependent selection
Hybrid	More accurate results than filter and wrapper with smaller feature subsets Less prone to overfitting than wrapper	Classifier-dependent selection
Ensemble	It is flexible and robust – as performance of feature selection methods don't depend on single subset It overcomes the instability problem of others. Constructs aggregate results to obtain the best results to individual methods	

Algorithm I
Multi-Filter based Feature selection approach

Input:	A training dataset D , Feature set $x_i = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{34}\}$, and class $c_i = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_6\}$, filter models: Info-gain, Gain ratio, chi-squared and ReliefF.
Output:	Subset of features
Procedure:	
1.	Let x_i be the feature set in the skin disease dataset, where $x_i = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{34}\}$ and $c_i = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_6\}$, where c_i represents the class.
2.	For each filter method, rank and sort the features x_i according to its importance in determining the output class c_i .
3.	Select two-third (2/3) split of each filter selection method's output x'_i .
4.	Combine selected output features x'_i of each method
5.	Determine the feature count threshold T and compute the feature occurrence rate among the filter methods
6.	Iteratively perform majority vote of common features. That is if count of common features is greater than or equal to T , select feature, otherwise drop feature. Where $T \geq 3$.
7.	Obtain reduced feature subset x'_i from all filters

E. Multi-embedded based Feature Selection Approach

The embedded feature selection models are the PREFEB, RFE-SVM and MIFEB. While the PREFEB and REF-SVM uses the prediction risk criteria and the recursive feature elimination criteria which combines feature selection with bagging of support vector machines (SVMs), so as to improve generalization performance of single learning machines also increases the diversity among individuals and shows that “many could be better than all”, the MIFEB uses the mutual information criteria employed to bagging of SVM.

- RFE-SVMs: The SVM classifier is used in the support vector machine recursive feature selection method to rank the features recursively and eliminate the least informative ones. This method recursively removing features by re-ranking them after each iteration based on their contribution to the SVM classifier [11, 38, 36] For linear SVMs the classification boundary equation is:

$$\hat{y}(x) = w^T \cdot x + b \quad (8)$$

where $\text{sign}[\hat{y}(x)]$ is the expected class feature vector (x), w is the weight vector, and b is a constant.

The SVM training process takes as inputs a training set of feature vectors and their corresponding class labels, and outputs a set of (N_{train}) parameters $\{\alpha_i\} = \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{N_{train}}\}$, where (N_{train}) is the number of training points. The parameters $\{\alpha_i\}$ can be used to calculate the weight vector w in the classification boundary equation 9:

$$w = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{train}} \alpha_i y_i x_i \quad (9)$$

As a result, the ranking criterion used in this method is:

$$c_j = (w_j)^2 \quad (10)$$

The SVM-RFE uses equations 8 and 9 to calculate the ranking criterion values c_j after training an SVM with the entire set of features for each feature j . The feature with the lowest c_j value is removed from the training set and placed at the bottom of the ranked feature set that results. The last remaining training feature is used to retrain the SVM, and the process continues until the training list is empty of any features. The ranked features list that results now contains the entire feature set in a logical order. The SVM-RFE output is an ordered feature set from which the top m features for classification are chosen. The outline of the linear SVM-RFE algorithm is shown in algorithm 2.

Algorithm II
RFE-SVMs

Inputs:	Training Samples $\{x_i, y_i\}$
Output:	Ranked features list R
Initialize:	$S = \{1, 2, \dots, D\}, R = \emptyset$
While S is not empty, do:	
1.	Restrict the features of X_j to the remaining S
2.	Calculate weight vectors after training SVM
3.	compute the ranking criteria $c_k = w_k^2, k = 1, \dots, S $
4.	obtain features with least value of c_k , referred to as feature p
5.	Add feature p into $R (R = (\{p\} \cup R))$
6.	Remove feature p from $S (S = \frac{S}{p})$

F. Prediction Risk based Feature sElection for Bagging (PRIFEB)

- The PRIFEB is an embedded feature selection model that uses the prediction risk criteria to rank and select

features. [26] proposed the PRIFEB, which evaluates each feature by estimating the data sets' prediction error when the values of all examples of this feature are replaced by their mean value [23]. That is PRIFEB uses the sequential forward search approach to search and find the best subsets at each increasing cardinality (Liu and Yu, 2005). The outline of the PRIFEB approach is illustrated in algorithm 3.

$$S_i = Err_{Test}(\bar{x}^i) - Err_{Train} \quad (11)$$

Where Err_{Train} and Err_{Test} represents the training and testing errors respectively, with the mean value of the i th feature defined as:

$$Err_{Train}(\bar{x}^i) = \frac{1}{l} \sum_{j=1}^l (\bar{y}(x_j^1, \dots, x_j^i, \dots, x_j^D)) \neq y_j \quad (12)$$

Where l and D are the number of examples S_i and features, respectively; \bar{x}^i is the mean value of the i th feature; and $\bar{y}()$ is the prediction value of the j th example after the value of the i th feature is replaced by the mean value. Finally, the feature corresponding with the smallest will be deleted, because this feature causes the smallest error and is the least important one.

Algorithm III
PRIFEB approach

Input: Training data set $S_r(x^1, x^2, \dots, x^D, C)$,
number of individuals T

Output: Ensemble model N

Procedure:

For $k=1: T$

1. Generates a training subset S_{rk} from S_r by bootstrap sampling algorithm, the size of S_{rk} is $\frac{3}{4}$ of S_r .
2. Train individual model L_k on the training subset S_{rk} using SVMs and compute Err_{Train} .
3. Using Equation (11) calculate prediction risk value R_i .
4. If R_i is greater than 0, the i th feature is selected as one of the optimal features. Repeat until features in S_{rk} are computed.
5. Generate optimal features $S_{rk-optimal}$ features from S_{rk} .
6. Train the individual model N_k on the $S_{rk-optimal}$ features using SVM.

End

Ensemble obtained models N using majority voting for classification.

- MIFEB: While the above-mentioned embedded feature selection model depends on the learning machine using the prediction risk criteria and the recursive feature elimination criteria, the MIFEB uses the mutual information criteria with bagging of SVMs. Mutual information is a widely used information theoretical measure for the stochastic dependency of discrete random features. It describes the statistical dependence of two random features on the amount of information that one feature contains about the other. In terms of the probability distribution of intensities,

the mutual information between two features R and S can be defined as follows:

$$I(R:S) = \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{s \in S} P\{r, s\} \log \frac{P\{r, s\}}{P\{r\} \cdot P\{s\}} \quad (13)$$

Where $P\{r, s\}$ is the combined probability distribution of intensities of two features R and S . $P\{r\}$ and $P\{s\}$ are the individual probability distribution of intensities of R and S respectively. The basic steps of MIFEB are described in algorithm 4.

Algorithm IV
MIFEB approach

Input: Training data set $S_r(x^1, x^2, \dots, x^D, C)$,
number of individuals T

Output: Ensemble model N

Procedure:

For $k=1: T$

1. Generates a training subset S_{rk} from S_r by bootstrap sampling algo., the size of S_{rk} is $\frac{3}{4}$ of S_r .
2. Employ the MI in Equation (13) on the training subset S_{rk} and obtain the value vector MI
3. Rank the vector MI in descending order and sum MI to obtain sum(MI)
4. Select all features whose total values is greater than $RMI * \text{sum}(MI)$. where RMI is a predefined ratio in the range $\{0,1\}$
5. Generate optimal features $S_{rk-optimal}$ features from S_{rk} according to the optimal features obtained.
6. Train the individual model N_k on the $S_{rk-optimal}$ features using SVM

End

Ensemble obtained models N using majority voting for classification.

F. An Ensemble Multi-Feature Selection (EMFME-FS) Approach

Our proposed EMFME-FS approach uses the output of the multi-filter based selection method described in algorithm 1 with the individual ensemble methods in algorithms 2, 3, and 4 respectively. The multi-filter method is a first step pre-processing phase prior to the use of the multi-embedded methods which finally selects the best optimal feature subsets before using a learning algorithm. The IG, gain ratio, chi-squared and ReliefF filter methods are used to rank the feature set of the original datasets to create a mutually exclusive subset before selecting two-third split of the ranked features (i.e., 22 features). These features are considered as the features with high descriptive and importance values with respect to each filter method at this stage. The final single feature subset output of the multi-filter methods is obtained by calculating the simple majority vote combining all filter methods. The feature subset obtained from the multi-filter methods are then passed through each embedded feature selection method for final optimal feature subsets which is then used for classification with bagging, boosting and stacking ensemble methods as described in algorithms 2,3 and 4. The EMFME-FS approach is illustrated in algorithm 5.

Algorithm V
Ensemble Multi-Feature selection approach (EMFME-FS)

Input: Training data set $S_{rk}(x^1, x^2, \dots, x^k, C)$

Output: Ensemble model N with metrics performance

Procedure:

1. Using feature subsets obtained from algorithm 1, perform REF-SVM, PRIFEB and MIFEB
2. For each feature subset i perform ensemble learning
3. Calculate performance metrics
4. Determine the best methods for classification

IV. MACHINE LEARNING CLASSIFIERS

In this study, five different machine learning classifiers including logistic regression as meta-classifier are used for prediction of the skin disease. These classifiers were selected as a combination of both homogeneous and heterogeneous classifiers as a result of the various type of ensemble method adopted in the study.

- Support Vector Machines (SVMs): The primary aim of SVM is to identify a hyperplane to maximize the margin between two different classes in a case of binary classification or multi class scenario using one-to-one or one-to-many approach. The hyperplane is described in Equation 8 above. Using the Lagrange multiplier techniques, the dual problem of the objective is shown in Equation 14 and 15.

$$\max_{\alpha} \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_i \alpha_j y_i y_j x_i^T x_j \quad (14)$$

$$s. t. \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i y_i = 0, \alpha_i \geq 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (15)$$

Once α_i is calculated, w can be obtained using Equation 9. The radial basis function is adopted as the kernel function and the regularization parameters as C and σ which are set to 100 and 10 respectively.

- Decision trees (DT): As one of the most frequently used algorithms in machine learning field, it is trained on a dataset for classification and regression analysis. Decision tree algorithm divides the data into various subgroups based on a sequence of questions. The process begins with the primary node, which is called the root of the tree and contains all samples. Each node is split into secondary nodes in either a multi-split or binary form. For the construction of the tree, the divide and conquer approach is followed. the approach checks whether all the training samples have the same label or not. Subsequently, the training samples that have different labels are represented in a separate subtree. The generation of a tree is a recursive procedure. The key challenge of the decision tree is the selection of the optimal partition attributes, which can be explained by information gain, gain ratio or Gini index. The algorithm is illustrated in (Lu et al., 2019).
- Naïve Bayes (NB): Naïve Bayes classifier is a probabilistic classifier based on the Bayes theorem assuming a strong (Naïve) independence of attributes. NB takes into consideration that all attributes (features) independently contribute to the probability of a certain decision. It independently analyzes all attributes of the data with equal importance and hence can be trained efficiently in a supervised learning scenario [27, 1].
- K-nearest neighbour (KNN): KNN is a non-parametric technique which is used to classify data points based on the distance function stored by the algorithm on the training dataset. The Euclidean distance is adopted in this study because it is used by most instance based learner [41, 47, 17]. To classify new instance, k-NN chooses the set of k objects from the training instances that are closest to the new data instance by calculating

the distance and assigns the label with two classes (brain tumour or normal). The Euclidean distance d between data point x and data point y are calculated using Equation 16.

$$d(x, y) = \sqrt{(\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - y_i)^2)} \quad (16)$$

Where testing vector $x = x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ and training vector $y = y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n$ in \mathbb{R}^2 vector space.

- Multilayer Perceptron (MLP): MLP is the popular “black box” artificial neural network architecture with backpropagation (a supervised learning algorithm) of machine learning algorithms. It has been shown that given the right size and the structure, MLP is capable of learning arbitrary complex nonlinear functions to arbitrary accuracy levels [12, 31]. In the MLP the input vector x_i multiplied by a weight vector w_i , and added to a bias b to produce an output \hat{y} using the following equations 17-20:

$$y_i = f(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b) \quad (17)$$

Where n is the number of input-output pairs, f is a non-linear activation function presented as:

$$f = \frac{1}{1 + \exp^{-x_i}} \quad (18)$$

To determine the prediction error of MLP, the Mean Square Error (MSE) function is applied as:

$$E(\hat{y}, y) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y} - y)^2 \quad (19)$$

Where E is the error function between the predicted class \hat{y} and the target class y . Also the training of the MLP by backward propagation involves computing the gradient of the error with respect to w using chain rule of differentiation as follows:

$$\delta_i = \frac{dE}{dw} \quad (20)$$

Where δ_i is the gradient descent, w represent weight. Thereafter, w is updated in the direction via the gradient that helps to minimize the loss. This study adopts one hidden layer MLP as it gives the best accuracy [34].

V. ENSEMBLE METHODS

The main idea of ensemble methodology is to combine a set of models, each of which solves the same original task, in order to obtain a better composite global model, with more accurate and reliable estimates of decisions than can be obtained from using a single model. In the literatures, combining outputs of multiple classifiers reduces the generalization error. Ensemble methods are categorized as either homogeneous (similar models) or heterogeneous dissimilar models). In this study, both categories are used through boosting, bagging and stacking ensemble methods [44].

A. AdaBoost

AdaBoost [37, 49, 50] uses the iterative ensemble method to combine weak classifiers to create a strong classifier that performs well. The underlying idea of AdaBoost in each boosting iteration is to set classifier weights and train data samples to accurately predict a class target of a given data instance with two classes using the average majority vote shown in Equation 21.

$$\sum_{t=1}^T w_t d_{t,j}(x) = \max_{j=1}^C \sum_{t=1}^T w_t d_{t,j}(x) \quad (21)$$

Where $d_{t,j}(x)$ represents support given by the t^{th} classifier to the j^{th} class for the instance x , w_t is the weight of classifier t and T is the total number of classifiers.

B. Bagging

Bagging [49, 50], which is derived from bootstrap aggregation, is the simplest but most powerful independent ensemble method for improving the accuracy of unstable learning algorithms. Datasets are distributed into various bootstrap replicates during the bagging process. Each replicate is made by replacing data from the original dataset; each replicate contains an average 63.2% of the original data. The procedure entails repeatedly putting the slow learner through a series of bootstraps. Each iteration combines the weak learner's classifier into a strong composite classifier, resulting in higher accuracy than any single component classifier could achieve alone. Finally, using the majority voting scheme (or plurality voting) represented in Equation 16, the aggregate of all base learners is computed.

$$\sum_{t=1}^T d_{i,j} = \max_{j=1}^C \sum_{t=1}^T d_{t,j}(x) \quad (22)$$

Where the decision of the t^{th} classifier is defined as $d_{t,j} \in \{0,1\}$, $t = 1, \dots, T$ and $j = 1, \dots, C$, where T is the number of classifiers and C is the number of classes. If t^{th} classifier chooses class ω_j , then $d_{t,j} = 1$, and 0, otherwise.

C. Stacking

stacking [28] is employed as an ensemble technique to combine models heterogeneously with the help of a meta-classifier. By the meta-learner, the method tries to induce which classifiers are reliable from the one that is not. The instance is first classified by each base classifiers. The classification is then fed into a meta-level training set from which a meta-classifier is produced. The classifier combines the different predictions into a final one. In stacking, the original dataset is partitioned into two subsets. The first is reserved to form the meta-dataset and the second is used to build the base-level classifiers. Consequently, the meta-classifier predictions reflect the true performance of base-level learning classifiers. Five base classifiers: SVM, DT, NB, KNN and MLP are trained with whole training dataset and then meta-classifier is applied on the outputs from the base classifier to produce final prediction results.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this paper, we developed a novel methodology for feature selection approach by combining multiple filter based feature selection models using some selected filters like Info Gain, Gain Ration, ReliefF and Chi-square to generate different feature subsets. Twenty-two features were selected in each subset (i.e., two-third of the 34-original features). Then using the simple majority voting technique, single thirteen features were selected for the embedded feature selection methods. The PRIFEB, MIFEB and RFE based on SVM model were then used to finally obtain nine features for base classifier ensemble learning method – bagging, boosting and stacking. The results obtained at each stage are as follows. Figs 2-5 shows the

different features obtained by the filtering methods. Out of these features two-third top highest scores were selected. Tables 4 depicts the accuracies obtained from the best features obtained from the PRIFEB, MIFEB and RFE-SVM embedded selection models.

Figure 2 Info Gain Figure 3 Gain Ratio Figure 4 ReliefF Figure 5 Chi-square

After running each base models for five time the accuracies and other measure scores obtained are shown in Table 4. In terms of accuracy, the individual and ensemble models perform well, except for the Boosted SVM which had 46.3% accuracy. The reason for the low performance of the boosted SVM is due to the poor selection of the hyper-parameter values obtained. The highest performing models in terms of accuracy are the base SVM, bagged decision tree, boosted decision tree using the majority and weighted majority voting techniques respectively and Stacking of all models using logistic regression as the meta classifier. Fig. 6 depicts the accuracies of all models in one chart. The model with the highest sensitivity is the stacked ensemble model with 85.8% sensitivity, whilst specificity is 97.4%. others within the range on specificity are KNN, bagged SVM, bagged MLP with 97.3%, 97.1% and 97.2% respectively. The highest precision is the stacked ensemble with 86.1% and 85.8% and 84.9% recall and f1 score respectively. From Table 4, it shows that stacking models heterogeneously can produce models with better classification performance.

Table IV

Metrics measurement table.

Base Classifiers	Accura cies	Sensiti vity	Specifi city	Precisi on	Recall	F1 score
SVM	0.9285	0.8251	0.9712	0.8189	0.8250	0.8088
DT	0.9047	0.8184	0.9652	0.7727	0.8183	0.7716
MLP	0.8780	0.8157	0.9699	0.7873	0.8156	0.7873
KNN	0.9047	0.8513	0.9730	0.8546	0.8513	0.8404
NB	0.7073	0.6449	0.9438	0.5131	0.6449	0.5276
Bag(SVM)	0.8809	0.8251	0.9712	0.8189	0.8250	0.8088
Bag(DT)	0.9286	0.8133	0.9688	0.7932	0.8133	0.7902
Bag(MLP)	0.8809	0.8315	0.9724	0.8297	0.8315	0.8134
Bag(KNN)	0.9047	0.8187	0.9700	0.8099	0.8186	0.8041
Bag(NB)	0.7317	0.7128	0.9495	0.7890	0.7127	0.6500
Boost(SVM)	0.4634	0.1667	0.8333	0.0242	0.1666	0.0423
Boost(DT)	0.9286	0.7985	0.9639	0.7791	0.7985	0.7804
Boost(NB)	0.7073	0.6415	0.9426	0.5127	0.6414	0.5252
Stacking (Log Reg.)	0.9286	0.8578	0.9742	0.8611	0.8577	0.8485

The confusion matrix of the individual and ensemble models are illustrated in Figs 7-19. The box plot of the models is captured in Fig. 20. The box plots depict the accuracies of all the models adopted in this paper. From the box plot, it is evident that the highest performing model is the stacked ensemble learning model which combines all five models and a meta heuristic classifiers for classification of the dataset, whilst the worst model is the boosted SVM which shows sign of weak hyper-parameter values used for the SVM classification.

Figure 20. Box plot

VII. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study seeks to develop an ensemble of multi-feature selection approach using both the filter feature selection models and the embedded feature selection methods in reducing the size of the original features for skin disease dataset collected from UCI machine learning repository. This approach can be used for any large dataset for the purpose of classification. However, the scope of this study is restricted only for skin dataset using only three filters and three embedded models for selection of the features and some selected classification learning algorithms and the ensemble of them.

IX. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have been able to show that multiple feature selection algorithms can be ensemble together with the base classifier ensemble methods for classification of skin disease. The multi-feature selection approach has shown feature reduction which in turn reduced the time and space complexity of the algorithms. In this study, the stacked ensemble of different classifiers shows improvement than others in accuracy, specificity, sensitivity, precision, recall and F1 score. In the future we hope to expand the number of filter methods

and aggregate the filters based on types, ranking, search strategy and approaches (i.e., individual and subset evaluation). Given its ability to enhance learning algorithms performances, we also intend to create a hybrid ensemble models that incorporates their advantages in a single model so as to improve feature selection in obtaining the best optimal features that can be used for classification problems both binary and multiple classes using any type of learning algorithms.

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